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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE THYROID STATUS EFFECT
ON GLYCATED HEMOGLOBIN**Dr Muhammad Ahmed¹, Dr Abdul Muqeet², Dr Umer Anwar²¹ Medical Officer, Govt Said Mitha Hospital, Lahore² Nishtar Medical University, Multan³ Foundation University Medical College, Islamabad

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Abstract:

Introduction: Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) can be changed in different conditions. We assume that HbA1c levels may change, probably due to a thyroid condition that changes as a result of changes in the red blood cell cycle (RBC).

Aim: The objective of this study was to determine the effects of altered thyroid status on HbA1c levels in individuals without diabetes, with overt hyper- and hypo-thyroidism, and if present, whether such changes in HbA1c are reversed after achieving euthyroid state.

Place and Duration: In the Endocrinology department of Services Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Methods: Euglycemic individuals with overt hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism were selected. Age and gender controls were obtained. Baseline HbA1c and reticulocyte count (for assessment of red blood cell cycle) were calculated and compared in all patients. Then stable euthyroidism was obtained in a randomly selected subgroup and HbA1c and reticulocyte counts were re-assessed. HbA1c values and reticulocyte counts were compared to baseline in both groups.

Results: HbA1c was significantly higher in the group with hypothyroidism in the initially selected patients. HbA1c values in patients with hyperthyroidism did not differ significantly from controls. Reduced HbA1c levels and increased reticulocyte counts were significant in the hypothyroidism group with no significant change in glucose levels after treatment. HbA1c did not change significantly in the hyperthyroidism group after treatment. However, reticulocyte counts have decreased significantly.

Conclusion: It was found that the initial levels of HbA1c were significantly high in patients with hypothyroidism and significantly decreased after obtaining euthyroid without changing glucose levels. There were no significant changes in patients with hyperthyroidism at the beginning or after treatment. Our study suggests that caution should be exercised when interpreting HbA1c data in patients with hypothyroidism.

Keywords: test interpretation, HbA1c, thyroid function.

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INTRODUCTION:

Glycan hemoglobin (HbA1c) is considered an important marker of prolonged glycemic control. Recently, the American Diabetes Association has suggested the use of HbA1c as a diagnostic tool in pre-diabetes and diabetes¹. A value of 5.7 to 6.5% indicates pre-diabetes, whereas a value of ≥ 6.5 is considered diabetes. Various factors other than glycemic status may affect HbA1c levels, including impaired red blood cell cycle (RBC). Red blood cell rotation increases under thyrotoxicity, while hypothyroidism does the opposite². We assume that HbA1c levels may vary due to altered thyroid status, probably due to changes in red blood cell turnover³. Therefore, after 2 hours, we measured HbA1c levels in patients with diabetes or pre-diabetic hypothyroidism and people with thyrotoxicity according to fasting and plasma glucose criteria⁴. We also observed some patients and measured HbA1c again after reaching euthyroidism.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was held in the Endocrinology department of Services Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. Informed consent was obtained from natural persons. It took place for 2 years (December 2010 - November 2012). The study included patients of both sexes who were diagnosed with open primary hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism and were naive in treatment.

Symptomatic primary hypothyroidism was defined as free T4 below the lower limit of normal and thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) above 15 μ / ml. Hyperthyroidism was defined as free T4 and / or T3 above the upper limit of the normal range with TSH suppression. Diabetic patients (fasting plasma glucose 126 mg / dL [7 mmol / L] or 75 g plasma glucose 2 hours after ≥ 200 mg / dL [11.1 mmol / L] defined, glucose intolerance (IGT) (140 to 199 mg / between dl glucose in plasma is determined for 2 hours 75 g glucose (7.8-11 mmol / l)) or impaired fasting glucose (defined as fasting plasma glucose from 100 to 125 mg) / dl [5.6-6.9 mmol / l]. Both fasting and oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) were carried out in one day. Hemoglobin <60 ml / min), significant liver impairment (increased bilirubin [> 1 mg / dl], decreased albumin (500 mg / day) and exclusion of pregnant patients).

Age- and gender-matched healthy euthyroid and euglycemic persons were recruited as controls. At the start of the study, assuming that a difference in HbA1c of 0.5% among baseline subgroup would be

clinically meaningful and assuming that the standard deviation (SD) would be $\leq 0.5\%$ and keeping the power at 80% and $P = 0.05$; the sample size needed was calculated to be 17. Patients selected in this way (47 hypothyroidism, 34 hyperthyroidism and 46 controls) were also examined to estimate HbA1c and reticulocyte counts. HbA1c was measured by high performance liquid exchange chromatography using the Bio Rad D 10 HbA1c program, which was initially approved by the national glycohemoglobin normalization program, documented as the traceability of the reference reference method. Diabetes control and complications.

We could not track all patients due to logistical restrictions. Additionally, for analysis before and after observation, the required sample size was estimated at 10, which would be clinically relevant for a 0.5% change in HbA1c, maintaining 80% potency and $P = 0.05$, and an expected SD of 0.5%. Therefore, we decided to randomly monitor 30 patients with hypothyroidism and 30 patients with thyrotoxicity from the selected patient population listed above. All patients with hypothyroidism were treated with levothyroxine. Six patients with hyperthyroidism decided to have surgery and were excluded. Other patients with hyperthyroidism were treated with carbimazole. HbA1c was checked again for at least 3 months after euthyroid was established and stabilized. At this point, HbA1c levels and average HbA1c levels were checked again against their reference values. Fasting plasma glucose, 2-hour OGTT, hemoglobin and reticulocyte counts were also checked.

Reference variables were appropriately compared using the unpaired Student's t-test and the Mann-Whitney rank sum test. Paired Student's t-test and Wilcoxon's rank test, respectively, were used to compare the variables before and after treatment. Coefficients and relations between categorical variables were calculated using the chi square test. Pearson's correlation analysis was performed to assess the relationships between variables. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Sigma stat 3.5 software (Jandel Scientific Software) was used for statistical analysis. The results were corrected for possible mistakes, such as hemoglobin, using the same software.

RESULTS:

Initially, 59 patients with hypothyroidism and 58 patients with hyperthyroidism were examined, and 12 and 24 patients were excluded from the study [Fig. 1].

Figure 1: Consort diagram

Table 1 shows the main characteristics of the patients initially selected. Among these groups, 75 g of glucose shows that there is no significant difference in plasma glucose values after 2 hours. HbA1c was found to be significantly higher in the hypothyroidism group in the initially selected patients (median $\pm$ interquartile range 5.6 ± 0.07 [$38 \pm \text{mmol / mol}$] [hypothyroidism] and 5.2 ± 0.04 [$33 \pm 3 \text{ mmol / mol}$] [control]; $P < 0.001$) [Fig. 2]. HbA1c values in patients with hyperthyroidism did not differ significantly from the control (median $\pm$ interquartile range 5.3 ± 0.5 [$34 \pm 4 \text{ mmol / mol}$] [hyperthyroidism] and 5.2 ± 0.04 [$33 \pm 3 \text{ mmol / mol}$] [control]; $P = 0.174$) [Fig. 2].

Figure 2: Comparison of baseline glycated hemoglobin between groups

These observations did not change even after adjustment for hemoglobin.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics

	Hypothyroid (n=47)	Thyrotoxicosis (n=34)	Control (n=46)	P	
				Hypothyroid and control	Thyrotoxicosis and control
Age	35.8±9.4	38.3±11.6	37.9±10.6	0.3	0.89
Gender (male/female)	15/32	9/25	13/33	>0.5	>0.5
Fasting plasma glucose	87.2±7.8	89.6±6.3	89.4±5.5	0.126	0.882
2 h post 75 g glucose plasma glucose	106.8±14.1	114.4±14.5	111.6±12	0.127	0.351
Hemoglobin	12.1±1.46	12.4±1.2	12.4±1.13	0.302	0.983

The mean baseline reticulocyte count did not differ significantly between hyperthyroidism (mean $\pm$ SD -1.48 ± 0.49) and the control population (mean $\pm$ SD -1.33 ± 0.54). The mean reticulocyte count was lower in patients with hypothyroidism (mean $\pm$ SD -1.02 ± 0.5) compared to the control, and the difference was generally significant ($P = 0.07$). In addition, patients with hypothyroidism with a correlation coefficient of 0.502 and $p = 0.0003$ showed a significant inverse correlation with the number of HbA1c reticulocytes [Fig. 3].

Figure 3: Correlation between glycosylated hemoglobin and reticulocyte count of hypothyroid patients at baseline. In the second part of the study, two patients with hypothyroidism developed IGT during follow-up and were excluded from the analysis. One patient with hypothyroidism and four patients with hyperthyroidism was lost. 27 patients with hypothyroidism and 20 patients with hyperthyroidism were evaluated for final analysis. The mean follow-up was 21.3 ± 3.1 weeks in the hypothyroidism group and 22.6 ± 3.7 weeks in the hyperthyroidism group. In none of the group's plasma glucose values were significantly different on an empty stomach and 75 g OGTT at the beginning and after treatment. The decrease in HbA1c was significant in the hypothyroidism group after treatment and reaching euthyroid status (median $\pm$ interquartile range 5.7 ± 0.75 [39 ± 8 mmol / mol] [pre-treatment] and 5.4 ± 0.75 [36 ± 8 mmol / mol] [after treatment]; $P < 0.001$) [Fig. 4]. The number of reticulocytes in patients with hypothyroidism increased significantly after treatment (0.9 ± 0.575 vs. 1.9 ± 0.77 ; $p < 0.001$). After achieving euthyroid status, the change in HbA1c in the hypothyroidism group was no longer statistically significant after adjusting for changes in reticulocyte count (5.58 vs. 5.74 [37 vs. 39 mmol / mol]; $P = 0.37$).

Figure 4: Glycated hemoglobin change following treatment of hypothyroidism

HbA1c did not change significantly after treatment in the hyperthyroidism group. (Median $\pm$ interquartile range 5.35 ± 0.45 [35 ± 4 mmol / mol] [pretreatment] with 5.35 ± 0.3 [35 ± 3 mmol / mol] [final treatment]; $P = 0.332$) [Fig. 5].

Figure 5: Glycated hemoglobin change following treatment of hyperthyroidism

However, reticulocyte counts decreased significantly after treatment in the hyperthyroidism group (1.485 ± 0.56 vs. 1.035 ± 0.39 ; $p < 0.001$). At the beginning of the study, HbA1c levels were found in 23 (48.9%) of our 47 patients with hypothyroidism. 0.75.7 was found (i.e. HbA1c criteria for pre-diabetes). Of the 27 observed patients with hypothyroidism, 17 initially HbA1c was ≥ 5.7 . Six of these 17 patients had < 5.7 at the end of the study.

DISCUSSION:

Our study found that the median basal HbA1c level is significantly higher in patients with open hypothyroidism compared to the control population, although it had a similar glycemic status. The median HbA1c decreased significantly after thyroid hormone replacement⁵. Our findings Kim et al⁶. This effect is probably due to the low rate of red blood cell rotation in patients with hypothyroidism. Initially, the difference between HbA1c between the control group and patients with hypothyroidism was reported by Kim et al. It may be the duration of hypothyroidism in our patients (4 weeks after the

thyroid gland) than in ours (most likely with a longer history of natural diseases). Anantarapu et al⁷. In patients with hypothyroidism, HbA1c values were also shown to decrease after thyroid hormone replacement without increasing any fasting changes or OGTT values. Reticulocyte count increased after thyroid hormone replacement⁸. Although there was a difference in HbA1c levels in patients with hypothyroidism before and after stable euthyroidism, this difference was no longer statistically significant when the reticulocyte count was corrected, suggesting that changing red blood cell rotation is responsible for different levels.

Treatment of HbA1c in patients with hypothyroidism⁹.

In contrast, patients with hyperthyroidism had similar mean HbA1c compared to baseline control. We believe that this may be due to the stimulation of glycation by malonic aldehyde produced by lipid peroxidation caused by an excess of thyroid hormones. This phenomenon may counteract the increased turnover of red blood cells in patients with hyperthyroidism¹⁰. The mean HbA1c did not change significantly after treatment of hyperthyroidism, despite a significant change in reticulocyte count. One limitation of our study was that we could not directly measure the red blood cell turnover rate using an examination such as chromium 51 red blood cell analysis and reticulocyte counts for indirect red blood cell turnover assessment¹¹. We also could not measure the level of malonaldehyde. HbA1c is an important tool for monitoring glycemic status in patients with diabetes¹². Recently, ADA has suggested its use in the diagnosis of diabetes and pre-diabetes. 48.9% of our patients with hypothyroidism showed an inconsistent result of the diagnosis of pre-diabetes using plasma glucose (fasting and 75 g oral glucose load) and HbA1c level. 75.7. (39 mmol / mol). In contrast, 5.9% of patients in the hyperthyroidism group and 2.2% between controls showed this discrepancy¹³. In the second part of the study (17), 17 out of 27 patients in the hypothyroidism group had HbA1c ≥ 5.7 at the start of the study¹⁴⁻¹⁵. Six of these 17 patients had values

CONCLUSION:

Despite similar glucose levels, basal HbA1c levels were significantly higher in patients with hypothyroidism than controls. HbA1c significantly decreased with treatment in patients with hypothyroidism without significant change in glucose levels. There were no significant changes in patients with hyperthyroidism at the beginning or after treatment. Our study suggests that HbA1c data should be interpreted with caution in patients with hypothyroidism.

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